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ABSTRACT

Agni is the centre for all the basic metabolism happening in our body. Any kind of disruption in our agni will lead to various types of disorders relating to different systems of the body. Agni converts food in the form of energy, which is responsible for all the vital functions of our body. Therefore, Ayurveda considers that Dehagni is the cause of life, complexion, strength, health, nourishment, lusture, oja, teja (energy) and prana (lifeenergy).^[1] It acts as a very crucial centre for which it maintains health within the body. Similar issues which are more hyped nowadays as per the digestive disorders is indigestion (Ajeerna).^[2] Diet and food pattern plays a significant role in the overall health and well being. Where the persons are less aware of what basically is the indigestion (Rasasesha Ajeerna)?^[3] Rasa sesh ajeerna is one among the disease conditions which occurs due to the heavy and late night dinner.^[4] This kind of irresponsibility of the food intakes affects the seat of agni said as the "Yakrit". Liver perform and govern majority of metabolic activities but when it get damages the Bhutagni Paak Kriya's disturbance leads to disrupted state of Agni, it leads to the disorder leading to Ajeerna more focusing to Rasasesha ajeerna. Acharya Sushruta has stated pitta and agni are same as the karma and features of pitta and agni are equivalent hence in ajeerna and in disease related to it we can see signs of hepatic damage in Liver Biomarkers (LFT).

KEYWORDS: Agni, Ajeerna, Rasasesha Ajeerna, Bhutagni Paak Kriya, Yakrit, Pitta.**INTRODUCTION**

Samadosha, sama agni, sama dhatu mala kriya this is the state of the dosha which is proper leading to proper agni and formation of dhatu and mala is the way towards a healthy digestive power.^[5] Balance to the aforesaid leads to a healthy individual if disturbed leads to disease.^[6] When everything in the body remains neutral it is therefore said as anumana pramana that the agni is properly functioning.

Whatever type of food consumed by the individual first acts upon the jathragni in the GI Tract later on it gets transported to the liver for the Bhutagni paka and then the product of nutrition is processed in the tissues by the dhatavagni.^[7] Ajeerna is the disease which occurs due to the agnimandya and indirectly related to the agni of pittadhara kala. So this is the basic approach to treat a disorder related to the Agni and also the pitta. As in Ayurveda this is mainly referred to as Ama. Ama is the

component factor which majorly forms all the disease in the body of the human. When we eat food which is heavy or junk or in an irregular time period then the food remains unbroken leading to formation of a toxic component that is said as Ama this trident is formed due to the ajeerna.^[8]

This ama is toxic, sticky and from the central amashaya it moves towards the channels and blocks the channels in different directions and cites leading to strotorodha and formation of disease on that particular site. Mainly agnimandya that is the lesser digestive fire or weak digestive fire which is unable to digest the food which is left unprocessed and causes the Ajeerna.^[9] There is many symptoms which includes the belching, vomiting or pain in stomach. Persons who are obese and take lots of food which is junk, greasy, oily, fried articles ends up with the agnimandya and also then leading to ajeerna and on the later stage it leads to the indigestion.^[10]

AETIOLOGY OF AJEERNA

As per the Acharya when the individual have improper sleeping habits, adhyasana, visamasana, after eating food taking excess amount of water, having very unwholesome diet that is samasana, vega sandharana like nidra vata pureesha, danta patana, ati ashaan, eating food before the previous food is digested. Stale foods, juice immediately after food, refrigerated foods, excessive alcohol consumption. Duse to the aforesaid condition and the eating habits Pitta and Kapha dosha gets vitiated and produces ama leading to agnimandyata and then leading to ajeerna.^[11]

Types Of Ajeerna

As per the doshas there are 3 types of ajeerna described.^[12]

1. Ama ajeerna
2. Vidagdha ajeerna
3. Vistabhda ajeerna

1. Ama Ajeerna

It is absically caused due to the Kapha dosha involvement.

Features

- Area besides the eyes have puffiness.
- Face also appears as puffed.
- Nausea.
- Repetitive belching with the smell of food which is benign taken.
- Frothy saliva and also increased in saliva formation.^[13]
- Body is drowsy and heavy.

2. Vistabdha Ajeerna

When there is pure involvement of vata dosha.

Features

- Bloating abdomen.
- Pain in the abdomen.
- Fatigue.
- Pain all over the body parts.
- When stool and flatus is not removed.

3. Vidagdha Ajeerna

When there is involvement of pitta dosha

Features

- Chest discomfort.
- Burning sensation.
- Thirst.
- Sour belchings.
- Tiredness.
- Giddiness.
- Fainting.^[14]

4. Vilambika Ajeerna

It is caused due to vitiation of two doshas that is kapha and vata.

Features

- Laziness.
- Discomfort in the chest.
- Tiredness.
- Also associated with the ama.^[15]

5. Rasa Seshaja Ajeerna

Caused due to heavy and late night dinner.

Features

- Belching.
- Heaviness of the chest.
- More salivation.^[16]

SAMPRAPTI

**Intake of aharaaja, viharaja, mansika
Tridosha gets vitiated kapha gets aggravated
Jataragni imbalance
Agni mandya
Ajeerna**

SAMPRAPTI GHATAKA^{[17][18]}

- Dosha- Samana vata, Pachaka pitta.
- Dooshya- Pachaka agni, rasa, rasa dhatu.
- Adhistana- Amashaya, grahani.
- Srotas- Annavaaha this disorder involves in amashaya, grahani, pakwashaya, srotas rasa vaha srotas where the first ama is produced because of the involvement of agni.
- Dusti prakara- Sanga.
- Agni- Mandagni.
- Marga- Abhyantara marga.

Agni Nirpeksha Ama^[19]

It is a condition where the ama is not directly due to the improper agni or impaired agni. As the dosha derangements of the doshik component the primary pathology occurs. As the primary concept is when there is indigestion there occurs ama. As per Vagbhatta acharya he says that atimatra and guru anabhishtandhi ahara lead to formation of ama. Amashaya compresses the dosha and agitates all of them simultaneously. It activates as the poison and the effected in the local or releases as the whole systemic disorder. Stages of agni sapeksha ama can be seen in 4 stages that is agni and paka as follows.

a. Apakwa anna rupa ama: The agni which is vitiated due to its antural cause and its not able to digest even the laghu anna here when it gets as remnant and stays up and formed as ama.

b. Anna Rasa Rupa Ama: When the digestion is proper anna rasa undergoes the paripaka. When the jatharagni is disrupted which leads to no proper metabolism of annarasa the partial annarasa cannot be able to under go dhatwagni and the apkwa rasa is there in the pakwashaya and said to be the ama. And it stays in the amashaya and termed as the anna rasa rupa ama.

c. Mala Sanchaya Rupa Ama: If mala not excreted out and is inbuilt in more excess quantity in the intestine leading to mala rupa ama termed to be the mala sanchaya rupa ama.

d. Rasa Sesha Rupa Ama: Due to agnimandyatwam the ahara gets partially digested and some of them left undigested it is then termed as the rasa seshaja rupa ama.^[20]

Why must ayurveda approach this ?

As per ayurveda the Saama meda theory and also the sthoulya theory which says about the rasaseshaja ajeerna and also it is the prime cause for the fatty liver disorders. It also says that it can be the post effect of the rasa sesha ajeerna and protect special areas of the body and the head, kidneys, heart. Hence the ayurvedic science is finding out the appropriate treatment aspect.

Liver's Role In Fat Metabolism^[21]

The liver is the storehouse and also plays a crucial role in the fat metabolism processing the dietary fats and also storing energy. When we consume the heavy food which are high in saturated fats and trans fats can put much strain in the liver.

Why can heavy food at night harm the liver?

1. Digestive strain: When the person intake food nearing to the bedtime can slow down the digestion which leads to the poor nutrient absorption and leading to more pressure on the liver.

1. Increased load of toxins: When a person eats more greasy, oily, heavy meals in the night time introduces more toxins into the body via the liver.

2. Disturbed circadian rhythm: Eating late in the night can even disrupt the body's natural circadian rhythm which affects the body's normal detox process.

3. Insulin resistance: Consuming heavy food which is high in sugar and saturated fats will lead to insulin resistance and also risk liver damage.

Phalatrikadi kwatha^[25]

Haritaki	Known as the antioxidant, anti inflammatory adaptogenic properties.
Amlaki	Rich in vit C anti oxidant anti inflammatory.
Vibhitaki	Contains antioxidant anti inflammatory, antimicrobial property.
Patola	Antioxidant, antimicrobial
Kiratatikta	Antioxidant anti inflammatory, antimicrobial property. ^[25]
Nimba	Antioxidant anti inflammatory, antimicrobial property. ^[26]
Vasa	Antioxidant anti inflammatory, antimicrobial property. ^[27]
Katuki	Antioxidant anti inflammatory, antimicrobial property.

CONCLUSION AND RELEVANCE^[28]

The action of the drug Phalatrikadi kwatha along with the changes in the daily regimens and also terminate late night food consumption can help the metabolism and also the diseased condition to reduce. In the discussion of the eight herbal drugs used in this kwatha named Phalatrikadi kwatha can be used in the treatment of kosthashrita kamala, that is Hepatocellular jaundice, pandu, and other liver disorders. It is pitta hara, pitta rechaka, yakrituttejak, deepana, rechana, pachaka, shotohara, jwarahara yakrut and raktavikara. On the modern part herbo hepatoprotective have properties of cholegouge and cholertic action, hepatocellular regeneration, antioxidant action.^[29]

4. Increased fat accumulation: When we consume high fat food the liver stores excess fat in the form of triglycerides. Prolonged consumption can lead to accumulation of the fat in the liver cells causing fatty liver disease.

5. Inflammation and oxidative stress: Heavy food can trigger the inflammation and oxidative stress in the liver leading to damage or scarring.^[22]

Impact Of Fatty Liver Disease^[23]

Liver fibrosis is the scarring of liver tissue which can progress to cirrhosis. Liver cancer, type 2 diabetes causing the insulin resistance and pancreatic damage, Cardiovascular disease leading to heart disease and stroke.

Food That Can Contribute To Fatty Liver Disease^[24]

1. Processed meats: High in saturated fats and sodium.
2. Fried foods: High in saturated and trans fats.
3. High fat dairy products: High in saturated fats.
4. Refined carbohydrates: High in empty calories and added sugars.
5. Sugary drinks: High in sugar and calories.

Prevention

1. Maintaining healthy weight: Throgh a balanced diet and regular exercise.

2. Eating a balanced diet: Nutrient dense food and follow on whole nutrient food.

3. Staying hydrated: Plenty of water through out the day.

4. Limiting processed and high fat food: Avoid or limit foods that can contribute to fatty liver.

5. Managing stress: Engage in stress reducing activities.

RESULT

Nearly all the types of major metabolism that is bhutagni paka which happens in the body is governed by the yakrit itself, so any type of hepatic pathology which can be of any source like bacteria, drug etc hampers the metabolism and decreases bhutagni paka kriya leading to depreciation in all the metabolic activities related to the digestion then there the pitta quality also gets deprived where we see the symptoms like the rasa sesha ajeerna. Where in the Phalatrikadi kwatha having its hepatoprotective property helps to reduce the symptoms and also aids in the liver disorders.

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